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**IDENTIFICATION OF DAMAGES IN UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON
FIBER-EPOXY COMPOSITES WITH ARTIFICIAL FLAWS VIA
ACOUSTIC EMISSION TECHNIQUES**

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ABSTRACT

We report here an experimental investigation on mechanical, electrical and acoustic emission behavior of unidirectional carbon fiber epoxy composites with or without pre-cut plies that were tested in tension. Fiber and matrix fracture, delamination, splitting (or cracking along fibers) and friction of delaminated faces contributed to characteristic acoustic emission behavior. These can be discriminated on the basis of peak amplitude and event duration of observed acoustic emission signals. Advanced digital signal processing techniques were also employed. Auto-regression coefficients were used as feature vectors in pattern recognition analysis, which can distinguish signal types without resorting to the signal amplitude or duration. The pattern classification scheme successfully identified five distinct types of signals without relying on the peak amplitude information. By combining the conventional acoustic emission parameters and auto-regression analysis, it is expected that in-service damage assessment procedures can be developed using acoustic emission.

INTRODUCTION

In-service nondestructive inspection of composite structures is important in assuring the quality of such structures. Acoustic emission (AE) has been demonstrated to be one of a few techniques that form the basis of successful inspection procedures. Several hundred papers have been published so far on AE of fiber reinforced composites. In chemical processing industry, AE has proven to be extremely beneficial and, each year, thousands of composite

vessels have been evaluated using AE [1]. Inspection of composite booms for insulated manlift devices is another example in which AE has been valuable. However, it is still not possible to distinguish the origin of an emission from a single AE signal detected. Ideally, one wishes to know whether the detected signal is from the fracture of a fiber or from the delamination. Statistically, certain emission sources produce high amplitude acoustic emission while others generate long duration signals. Such information has been employed, but not always reliable due to the attenuation of AE signals in composite structures [2-5].

In this report, we consider the use of pattern recognition analysis, which can classify various features of AE signals and help identify their origins. In order to utilize computerized pattern recognition analysis procedures [2, 6] for quality assurance and for nondestructive testing, we must first characterize acoustic emission parameters for a given fracture mechanism in simple material systems. In particular, the fracture of flawed composites and the delamination of laminated composites are studied using unidirectional composites with some laminae cut at specific locations. For such unidirectional composites, fiber fracture and matrix fractures, i.e., delamination and splitting, are expected [7-9]. Standard acoustic emission parameters associated with specific failure mechanisms were also obtained via advanced acoustic emission instrumentation. Results are correlated to fracture behavior of these model composites.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Two types of samples with flaw were employed [4]. One had pre-cut laminae in the center within unidirectional tensile samples. This group of sample geometries is expected to generate stress concentration at the pre-cut laminae, leading to delamination and fiber fracture. The other type has all the laminae pre-cut with typically 1" overlap similar to lap joints. In such sample geometries, delamination is expected to be the primary failure mode.

Carbon fiber reinforced epoxy matrix composite sheets were produced by thermal compression method from a prepreg (Celion G-50 fibers / Hexcel F584 epoxy). Typically, 6" x 10" size sheets were produced at 350° F.

Tensile samples with nominal width of 1/2" were prepared from these unidirectional composite sheets. Only the fiber direction (0°) samples were made and their length was 10". Tapered PVC reinforcing tabs, 3" long, were glued to each end. The thickness of a sample was dependent on the number of laminae with a single lamina thickness of typically 0.005".

The mechanical testing was performed using a floor model Instron equipped with screw-assisted wedge grips. A crosshead speed of 0.01"/min was always used. Tests were conducted in room air at 70 to 75° F.

Acoustic emission tests were conducted during tensile testing. An acoustic emission sensor (a narrow band type, AET MAC175L or a semi-wideband type, MAC425) was placed on a sample at the center portion using a viscous couplant and springs. We used 60

dB or 40 dB gain preamplifiers with plug-in filters of 125 to 250 kHz and 30 kHz to 2 MHz. The preamplifier output was fed to a microprocessor-based acoustic emission signal processor (AET Model 5000A). Typically, only one input was processed in most tests, in order to gain a higher processing speed. This signal processor records the peak amplitude, signal duration, signal rise time, ringdown or acoustic emission counts of each burst-type acoustic emission signal. The rate of burst-emission signals and applied load were also recorded as a function of time. After a test, cross-plots of several parameters were made; e.g., the peak amplitude vs. signal duration. The rms voltages of acoustic emission signals were also recorded using two rms voltmeters, a multi-channel digital storage recorder and a two-pen recorder.

For pattern recognition study, waveforms of AE signals from MAC425 were selectively digitized and recorded. These were taken in separate tests that were interrupted for data transfer to a computer (IBM PC/AT) from a digitizer (Data Precision D6000). A sampling rate of 2 MHz was used. 1024 points were recorded for each signal. Major parts of signal processing were conducted on a Gould superminicomputer, running the ILS package from Signal Technology, Inc. under the UNIX (Berkeley, 4.2) operating system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fracture Modes and Strength

Three main modes of fracture were observed. The first type is fiber fracture at random locations or at a pre-cut lamina location. The second is splitting parallel to the load (or fiber) direction, followed by fracture of split composite at various locations. Final fracture is catastrophic. These two types are often accompanied by delamination as well. The third is delamination. When no continuous ply exists as in some composite sheets, the delamination leads to the so-called "tensile shear" fracture (of lap joints). Macroscopically, splitting was the most obvious mode when un-cut laminae are included, whereas only delamination was observed for the lap joint type samples. Random fiber fracture was noticeable only under a microscope.

When the splitting mode is observed, the final fracture always coincided with complete delamination, followed by fiber fracture within each split composite. Thus, the fracture load (stress) represents the start of macroscopic delamination. This is also the case for the delamination mode of fracture.

Observed range of effective fracture strength was 150 to 230 ksi when un-cut laminae are included. This agrees with typical values for carbon fiber-epoxy composites in the 0° direction. The tensile shear strength with one inch overlap was 1200 to 3500 psi, increasing with the thickness of composites. This range is also typical of epoxy adhesive joints.

Acoustic Emission

Figure 1a shows the plots of load vs. time and rms voltages of AE signals vs. time curves. The sample in this test was a six-laminae composite with two three-laminae group pre-cut, overlapping 2". This sample failed completely in tensile shear; that is, delamination of the overlap area led to failure. Strong AE signals were detected coinciding with load drops and nearing the final fracture. Noticeable AE activities started at about one-third of the maximum load level. The peak amplitude distribution of AE signals for this portion of the test is shown in Fig. 1b (90 to 125 s). The average peak amplitude of detected AE events was about 58 dB. The amplitude distributions of the later parts were similar except lower amplitude events down to 40 dB increased.

Considering these and other observations, the medium amplitude (50 ~ 75 dB) events were concluded to correspond to the initiation and slow growth of delamination. This is because initial AE events had the medium amplitude levels only. Even at the final fracture, this sample was stressed to only 43 ksi, making the fiber fracture unlikely. The high amplitude (> 75 dB), long duration (>200 μ s) events were attributed to rapid advances of the delamination, accompanied by load drops. Since this sample failed by delamination, this is the only plausible mechanism for the observed events during the final fracture. Examination of the fractured sample via optical microscopy also indicated no fiber fracture.

The second type of AE behavior is illustrated in Fig. 2a. This sample was a seven-lamina composite, the center single lamina of which was pre-cut. In the failed sample, no delamination was detected. One major and two minor splits were noted. The final fracture was due to fiber breakages at both ends (at the end of grip tabs). Acoustic emission as detected in the rms voltages started at the stress of 47.5 ksi. The fracture of carbon fibers were detected by microscopy above ~ 60 ksi. Typical peak amplitude distribution of AE signals from the initial 430 s segment is given in Fig. 2b. A prominent peak at 33 dB is evident (although the decreasing intensity below the peak was due to approaching threshold at 25 dB). The average peak amplitude level is about 35 dB and a higher amplitude tail extended to 78 dB (maximum in the present setting). However, AE events with amplitude levels above 45 dB constituted less than 10%. The average event duration was about 35 μ s. These short, low amplitude signals are expected to arise from the fracture of carbon fibers and the matrix. There were also events having the amplitude levels of 35 to 65 dB and the event duration exceeding 100 μ s. These medium amplitude signals are apparently due to splitting since no delamination was detected even in the fractured sample. These signals contribute to large spikes in the rms voltage-time curve and their numbers are comparable to that of delamination-induced AE signals (Fig. 1b). Since splitting is macroscopic crack propagation in the resin matrix at very low stresses and propagates slowly, longer AE event duration is expected.

Unidirectional samples with no intentional flaw (20 plies) showed peak amplitude

Figure 1: a) Load vs. time and the rms voltages of acoustic emission signals vs. time plots for a sample with a single lap joint. b) The peak amplitude distribution of acoustic emission signals for 90 - 125 s segment. The reference level for the amplitude levels is 0 dB at 1 μV at the sensor output.

Figure 2: a) Load vs. time and the rms voltages of acoustic emission signals vs. time plots for a sample with pre-cut mid-plices. b) The peak amplitude distribution of acoustic emission signals from the initial 430 s segment.

distribution characteristics similar to Fig. 2b. When a peak amplitude distribution curve taken at 20 to 40 ksi where only matrix cracks are expected is compared to those at higher stresses (after both were normalized), the latter showed increased activities at 40 to 55 dB. This suggests a shift in the peak amplitude distribution for the fiber fracture in comparison to the matrix fracture and higher AE activities due to splitting.

When both fiber fracture and delamination were observed, a peak amplitude distribution curve shown in Fig. 3 was obtained. This can be obtained by the superposition of Figs. 1b and 2b and was found in a nine-ply flawed (middle three plies pre-cut) sample at stresses of 140 to 156 ksi. These two peaks are apparently due to the fiber fracture and delamination.

The electrical resistance of a tensile sample was recorded in about 20 tests. While the initial resistivity was consistent, observed changes varied widely from 1.2 % to 9 %. Although a part of the changes were irreversible, the resistance increased toward the end of unloading. Apparently, fiber to fiber contacts play a significant role. No simple correlation of fiber fracture could be developed.

Three representative AE signals from a unidirectional samples with no intentional flaw are shown in Fig. 4. These are typical of low (<40dB), medium (40~60 dB) and high amplitude signals. Their frequency spectra and three coefficient autoregressive models (broken curves) are given in Fig. 5. AE signals were also digitized during unloading and from flawed samples. Using the first two reflection coefficients (deduced from the autoregressive models), cluster analysis was performed. Five classes of signals emerged as shown in Fig. 6. Classes A, B, and C correspond to those of Figs. 6 and 7. According to the amplitude levels, Classes A and B are expected to represent matrix cracking, fiber fracture and splitting, while Class C is likely to correspond to splitting. Class D is for signals during unloading that are most likely due to frictional sources, while Class E represents high amplitude signals from the delamination in a single-lap sample. All others signals analyzed could be classified to one of the five classes.

Following this training phase, 13 more tests were conducted using six different samples. Results of pattern classification using the maximum likelihood classifier are given in Table 1. From each test, we obtained digitized records of a different amplitude range of signals (low, medium and high). Unflawed (U), flawed with pre-cut mid-ply (F) and lap-joint (DL) samples were used. A majority of the signals were classified to Class B overall. Nearly a half of low amplitude signals were of Class A. Since Class A signals were not found in the DL sample in which the fibers would be unlikely to fracture, we assign Class A to fiber fracture. At present, it is difficult to assign either matrix cracking or splitting to Class B signals. Four out of seven high amplitude signals from the DL sample were Class E. This is not unexpected, but Classes B and C were also found indicating that the amplitude discrimination cannot be regarded as a reliable tool.

The present results demonstrate that this approach is effective in waveform classification.

Figure 3: The peak amplitude distribution of AE signals for a sample showing a bimodal distribution. The reference level for the amplitude levels is 0 dB at 1 μ V at the sensor output.

Figure 4. Typical AE waveforms of (a) low, (b) medium, and (c) high amplitude signals.

Figure 5. Frequency spectra and three coefficient autoregressive model (broken lines) of Class A (top), Class B (middle) and Class C (bottom) AE signals.

Since we have no independent method of verification, it is not possible to assess the validity of the particular assignment of AE mechanism to a classified pattern. However, the above assignments of fracture mechanisms to classified patterns appear to be consistent with the results of amplitude distribution and event duration analyses.

Figure 6. Cluster analysis plot using the first and second reflection coefficients. All five classes (A to E) are shown.

TABLE 1

Results of pattern classification of AE signals to five classes using the maximum likelihood classifier. Top: Unflawed samples. Bottom: Flawed (F and DL type) samples

	AAAA	BBBB	CCCC	DDDD	EEEE
UAAH			3		
UAAM		9	4	3	
UBAL	2	1		3	
UBAM		4	2		
UBAH		1	2		
	AAAA	BBBB	CCCC	DDDD	EEEE
DLAM		2	1		
DLAH		1	2		4
FAAL	5	5			
FAAM	1	1			
FBAL		4	1		1
FBAM		1	2		
FCAL	2	1	1		
FCAM		2			

In the present pattern recognition analysis, the amplitude of an AE signal was not included. This was a deliberate attempt to utilize only the waveform information. In future experiments, we need to incorporate the conventional AE parameters and the stress level at which a signal was recorded.

CONCLUSION

The present experiment confirms that acoustic emission techniques provide indications of different fracture processes in composites. The peak amplitude distribution and event duration of AE signals are most suited for real time statistical discrimination, but pattern recognition analysis offers a means of identifying individual AE signals on the basis of their waveforms.

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